

ETHICS IN SCIENCE

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Abstract: The specificity of ethics as a science of moral regulations of human exercise is singled out; characterizes the specifics of the quintessential norms of the ethics of science; the primacy of the norm of social obligation of a scientist is affirmed.

Keywords: specifics of ethics; the essence of the ethics of science; ethical requirements of science; human activity. Specificity of ethics; the essence of the ethics of science; moral necessities of science; human activity.

Ethics (Greek etika, from ethos - custom, disposition, character) is a philosophical self-discipline that looks up morality, morality. as a designation of a one of a kind location of study, the term "ethics" used to be first used through the historical Greek logician Aristotle (384-322 BC). in the self-discipline of current scientific activity, ethics research the specifics of ethical relationships every indoors the scientific local itself and between science and society as a whole, defining a set of values, norms and policies in these areas.

In everyday life, ethics is commonly understood as the requirements that govern our behavior. The world standard Canadian physiologist Hans Selye (1907-1982) believed that scientists as a social crew have applicable cause to fear about their ethics, their frame of mind to work and people. in particular, he wrote: "The awesome enthusiasm and desire to achieve excellence in any location is so all-consuming that a persona risks turning into a fairly specialised and directed via a single intention like a robot. that is why it is so natural for a scientist to ask himself from time to time whether or now not or no longer his conduct corresponds to the set cause and, larger importantly, whether or not or no longer or no longer the intention is valuable of the efforts made to acquire it" (cited in [22, p. 98]). Selye stated that "in the entirety that issues work, scientists strive to be scrupulously easy with themselves..." (quoted from:

[22, p. 99]). In his complete life, Hans Selye knew entirely two human beings who deliberately falsified their scientific results, however each have been mentally unstable. on the other hand ". Diseases of one type or each and each and every other have an impact on all professions. But most frequently it is the younger scientist who, succumbing to his enthusiasm, needs to see definitely what he wishes (hereinafter, it is highlighted with the beneficial useful resource of us. - Auth.). Here you need to be on the lookout. the most gorgeous concept is in hazard of being destroyed by means of a single unlucky reality - it is solely a rely of successfully perceiving this situation. I be aware of from trip that if a principle used to be absolutely great, its destruction does now no longer turn into a defeat, alternatively into a victory. it will lead to an even extra fruitful theory, without prejudice to the splendid facts, which certainly acquired proper here to mild in opposition to the historical previous of the devalued facts" (cited in [22, p. 99]).

Theoretical ethics is a philosophical science about the essence and ordinary traits of morality. theoretical ethics gives many paradigms and concepts, author's variations of the essence of morality, handy concepts, functions of the beliefs of goodness, humanity and justice. the author's necessities of theoretical ethics can be studied the utilization of the capacity of look up with the useful resource of persona scientists or in the shape of a "philosophical workshop" with educational wishes and aims of human socialization [8; 9; ten]. the important paradigms of theoretical ethics in accordance to the criterion of freedom of wish of a character - self sustaining ethics, heteronomous ethics; in accordance to the criterion of the dreams of human challenge - eudemonistic, hedonistic, utilitarian, perfectionist paradigms of theoretical ethics.

Autonomous ethics - a paradigm of theoretical (philosophical) ethics, exploring the essence and residences of morality and morality the use of the hypothesis of the independence of morality from one-of-a-kind classes of culture - religion, law, art, ideology - and its interior natural self-organization on the beliefs of humanity moral accountability and similar ethical values that a man or girl chooses of his very non-public free will. heteronomous ethics is a paradigm of theoretical (philosophical) ethics that explores the essence and residences of morality and morality the utilization of the speculation of the dependence of morality on extraordinary varieties of cultural directions that restriction the free preference and free will of a person, the action of exterior explanations (factors).

applied (practical) ethics - the science of precise troubles and the utility of moral norms and ideas of normative ethics in particular conditions of ethical choice. From the 2nd 1/2 of of the twentieth century The following teaching of utilized ethics are relevant: bioethics; pc ethics; scientific ethics;

Professional ethics; social ethics; political ethics; environmental ethics; ethics of business relations (ethics of commercial enterprise communication); ethics of science; enterprise ethics; criminal ethics; different types.

Researchers of the issues of science and tradition have proposed more than a few versions of the rationalization of the essence and specifics of science. for instructional purposes, the hypothesis is substantiated: “science is a specialized machine of ideal, sign-semantic and material-objective recreation of people, aimed at attaining the most reliable true knowledge about reality” [11, p. 28]. in the summary sense, the thinking of "science" denotes unique states of human pastime related with the creation, distribution, exchange and consumption of information, authentic information about the objects of being and the building of new objective objects, or artifacts of culture, having "material and information price for enhancing human lifestyles and systems of society” [12, p.22].

In explaining the essence of science, it is fundamental to take into account the concept of “anti-chaos essence of science” [13, p. 338-339; 14, p. 30-32]. the essence of science in this notion is related with the content of human activity: “activity is the anti-chaos attention of being” [15], its unique classification is human activity. the specificity of science as an asset of the cultural trip of mankind lies in the manufacturing and consumption of actual ideal expertise and fabric inventions, which are the end result of the transformation of the **chaos of objects of being into states of information of optimizing people’s lives.** for science, this summary generalization capability its (science) characterization as an innovative anti-chaos exercise of specialists and consumers of statistics and innovations with the goals of progress in alleviation and satisfaction of prevalent human wants in conditions of most completeness objective and innovative know-how of the actual houses of the limitless object of being [16, p.157-158]. The ethics of science as a kind of utilized ethics was created through specialists in the philosophical and sociological sciences for the normative rules of the things to do of science workers. The ethics of science refers to the device of sociocultural norms of science, or to the machine of sociocultural willpower (conditionality) of science. sociocultural norms of science are represented by using structures of moral and legal normative elements of scientific activity. There are a variety of author’s selections for describing the socio-cultural conditioning of science [17; eighteen]. in an abstract description "ethics of science is a gadget of requirements for the applicable behavior of scientists and individuals employed in science in their interpersonal interactions primarily based on compliance with moral

precepts" [7, p. 204; 12, p. 34]. The ethics of science creates a specific system of connections in science, which is known as the moral foundations of science. the thought of the moral basis of science is formed with the aid of the logical technique of "isolating abstraction" [19, p. 20-21], in which, out of the many states of exercise of scientists, signs of the diploma of implementation of ethical norms in the machine of science are distinguished. ethical norms of behavior of subjects of science incorporate regular policies of human interaction and are supplemented with the aid of professionally vast requirements for the implementation of a virtuous life in the implementation of research activities. the fundamental moral norms of science were established: disinterested search for truth, democratic universalism, ban on plagiarism, novelty of the scientific result, validity of the scientific result, openness of the results obtained, geared up skepticism, freedom of scientific creativity, social responsibility [7, p. 204-205; 20, p.64-65]. The listed ethical norms create an highest quality mode of interaction between scientists and professionals engaged in expert things to do of acquiring understanding and growing material inventions. disinterested search for reality as an ethical norm of science capacity the state of a scientist's activity, in which the foremost motive or cause for his pastime is acquiring the maximum feasible actual know-how and cloth invention, but not achieving the most cloth advantages of life. the advantages of life, which include a decent salary, at easy existence and a high cloth stage of well-being, are furnished to the scientist by means of the state, employers and society as a entire as a reward for new scientific effects in understanding the authentic properties of an object and invention. democratic universalism of science is the norm of behavior of scientists, according to which all social companies and men and women can work in the machine of science and consume its achievements to the extent of their desires and abilities. The ban on plagiarism is the obligation of the situation of science now not to use the scientific achievements of others scientists as their personal and besides indicating the authorship of professionals who have until now bought comparable or same results. The novelty of a scientific end result as an ethical norm of conduct of a scientist is expressed in the advent of previously unknown information about an object, strategies and means of its cognition, processes of systematizing records and its software in practice. the validity of the scientific end result - the responsibility of the scientist to contemporary the effects of his effects of cognition by using capacity of the laptop of signal means. Significant potential of science ought to be reachable to the understanding of the scientific community, comply with the insurance policies of logical thinking, be set up in experiments and be constant with traditionally set up buildings of know-how and scientific fashions of the theoretical explanation of the object. Organized skepticism is a rule of conduct for scientists, in

accordance to which every of them can unique practical doubt about the reality of the outcomes obtained, regardless of the social or professional fame of the man or woman who claims his achievements. this rule is very quintessential for the growth of science, considering the fact that scientists can be mistaken, and verification of the truth of their lookup consequences is consistently quintessential and carried out as a potential of attaining the objective truth of appreciation and qualimetric symptoms of fabric inventions. Openness, or accessibility of the effects acquired - a requirement for a scientist now not to hide new knowledge from experts and humanity and be certain to make it reachable to them in accordance with usual standards for replicating books and articles, open data in the shape of speeches and reports in the the front of an audience. Freedom of scientific creativity is the potential of a scientist to independently pick the object and potential of cognition, to arrange the cognitive manner in accordance with his personal competencies and desires in the absence or with minimal external coercion. the social responsibility of the state of affairs of science is the u . s . a . of issue of one's non-public freedom of creativity realized through the scientist, if freedom acts as a skill of immoral and unlawful actions, contradicts the ideals of humanity, goodness and justice [21, p. 234-235].

The moral norms of the ethics of science are inadequate capability of organizing the matters to do of those employed in science and are supplemented with the useful resource of a system of legal aid for the functioning of science in society. The reliable legal guidelines of science management set up by using the use of the professionals of a specific state, in unity with the norms of the ethics of science, refer to an brilliant computer of hyperlinks between the factors of the content fabric of science and its hyperlinks with specific factors of public life. the direct magnitude of the moral norms of science is characterized by using the country of "stability", thinking about morality in its essence is the most steady device of informational humanitarian law of human activity. The scientist's focal point of the norm of social responsibility is the predominant norm of the ethics of science, on account that in the chaos of social life, for extra than a few reasons, inhumane techniques of social interactions can prevail. for example, in the 20s of the 21st century, the desirable of the humans to self-determination and human rights, agreed and permitted by using using the states of mankind through the UN record gadget in 1946-1948, are implemented in accordance to the "double standard" criterion. the moral that capacity of the "double standard" criterion in respecting the rights of the human beings and the personality is to obtain "permission" for the implementation of human rights from character elites and states, ignoring the results of referendums and special democratic kinds of managing human things to do [22, p. 30-32]. the norm of the scientist's social accountability is

contradictory due to the functioning of the "double standard" criterion; the scientist is compelled to act pragmatically, identifying on between the beliefs of proper and evil. ideally, regardless of the "double standard" of morality and different techniques of regulating the behavior of a scientist, respect for human rights and different humanistic requirements of conduct characterizes the essential content material fabric of the social duty of science.

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